

Synthesis and antimicrobial activities of new 1,4-benzothiazines possessing thiazolyl/imidazolyl moieties

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Manuscript received 30 May 2001, revised 27 March 2002, accepted 5 April 2002

3-[4'-Methyl-2'-(4''-substituted-phenyl)thiazol-5'-yl]-1,4-benzothiazine hydrobromides (3A) and 3-[1'-(4''-substituted-phenyl)-2'-mercapto-4'-imidazol-5'-yl]-1,4-benzothiazine hydrobromides (3B) were synthesized. 5-Acyl-4-methylthiazoles (1A) and 5-acyl-2-mercapto-4-methylimidazoles (1B) were brominated using phenyltrimethylammonium tribromide as selective brominating agent to obtain the corresponding bromoacyl products 2A and 2B. These bromoacyl products when cyclocondensed by refluxing with 2-aminobenzenethiol in alcohol yielded the title compounds 3A and 3B. They were screened against microorganisms.

We have already reported the synthesis of thiazoles¹ (1A) and imidazoles² (1B). Phenyltrimethylammonium tribromide PTT, a regioselective α -brominating agent to get α -bromoketones³, was employed to brominate the acylthiazoles (1A) so as to obtain 5-bromoacyl-4-methyl-2-(4'-substituted-phenyl)thiazoles (2A). Compounds 2A on

cyclocondensation with 2-aminobenzenethiol in refluxing alcohol gave 3-[4'-methyl-2'-(4''-substituted-phenyl)thiazol-5'-yl]-1,4-benzothiazine hydrobromides (3A) (Scheme 1). Bromination of the imidazoles (1B) was carried out with the aid of PTT in refluxing acetic acid to get 1-phenyl-2-mercapto-4-methyl-5-bromoacylimidazoles (2B). The bromoacylimidazoles (2B) were then cyclocondensed with 2-aminobenzenethiols to yield the title compounds, imidazolyl-1,4-benzothiazine hydrobromides (3B). The physical data of the compounds are recorded in Table 1.

Scheme 1

Table 1. Physical data of compounds 2A, 3A, 2B and 3B

Compd. no.	R	R'	Yield %	M.p. °C
2A-a	H	—	78	114
2A-b	OCH ₃	—	75	90
2A-c	Cl	—	70	116
3A-a	H	—	70	256
3A-b	OCH ₃	—	75	265
3A-c	Cl	—	70	260
2B-a	H	—	58	195
2B-b	Cl	—	52	207
2B-c	CH ₃	—	60	240
2B-d	OCH ₃	—	63	215
3B-a	H	H	60	205
3B-b	H	CH ₃	50	180
3B-c	H	OCH ₃	54	175
3B-d	H	OC ₂ H ₅	56	150
3B-e	CH ₃	H	55	109
3B-f	CH ₃	CH ₃	60	135
3B-g	CH ₃	OCH ₃	65	162
3B-h	CH ₃	OC ₂ H ₅	53	132
3B-i	OCH ₃	H	58	182
3B-j	OCH ₃	CH ₃	54	152
3B-k	OCH ₃	OCH ₃	52	108
3B-l	OCH ₃	OC ₂ H ₅	56	201
3B-m	Cl	H	62	218
3B-n	Cl	CH ₃	60	138
3B-o	Cl	OCH ₃	55	178
3B-p	Cl	OC ₂ H ₅	56	162

Some of the compounds were screened against fungi like *Aspergillus flavus*, *Helminthosporium oryzae* and bacterias like *Xanthomonas campestris* and *Bacillus subtilis* by using filter paper disc method at 250 and 500 ppm concentrations. The compounds with methoxy and chloro substituents showed inhibition at higher concentration towards the test organisms and as such there was no marked enhancement in the inhibitory property of the thiazolyl-1,4-benzothiazine hydrobromides (3A) when compared with the respective acyl thiazoles (1A).

The imidazolyl-1,4-benzothiazine hydrobromides (3B) were screened against plant pathogens *Alternaria brassicae* and *Gloeosporium ampelophagum* at 100 and 250 ppm. All compounds showed moderate stimulatory activity against the test organisms. The compounds with ethoxy and chloro substituents exhibited marked stimulation against the test organisms even at 100 ppm concentration.

Experimental

All m.ps. are uncorrected. The purity of the compounds was checked by TLC. IR spectra (nujol/KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 1430 spectrophotometer and PMR spectra (CDCl₃) on a Bruker AMX-500 FT NMR spectrometer (300 MHz) using TMS as an internal standard.

5-Bromoacyl-4-methyl-2-(4'-chlorophenyl)thiazole (2A-c) : A mixture of 2-(4'-chlorophenyl)-4-methyl-5-acyl-thiazole (1A-c; 0.01 mol, 2.47 g) and phenyltrimethyl ammonium tribromide (0.01 mol, 3.76 g) in anhydrous THF (100 ml) was stirred at room temperature for 6 h and filtered. The filtrate was evaporated to dryness by removing THF under vacuum. The product obtained was treated with water, filtered, dried and crystallized from methanol-DMF mixture : ν_{\max} 1700–1680 (COCH₂Br, arom. C=O), 1280–1270 (CH₂Br, wagging), 760 cm⁻¹ (C–Br) and characteristic absorptions of thiazole and benzenoid nuclei were also noted; δ (CDCl₃) 2.79 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.30 (2H, s, COCH₂Br), 7.42 (2H^a, d, *J* 8 Hz, ArH), 7.89 (2H^b, d, *J* 8 Hz, ArH).

3-[4'-Methyl-2'-(4''-chlorophenyl)thiazol-5'-yl]-1,4-benzothiazine hydrobromide (3A-c) : A solution of 5-bromoacyl-4-methyl-2-(4'-chlorophenyl)thiazole (2A-c; 0.01 mol, 3.05 g) in ethanol (50 ml) was slowly added to a solution of 2-aminobenzenethiol (0.01 mol, 1.25 g) in ethanol (50 ml) and the mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for 3 h. The resulting yellow solid was crystallized from methanol-DMF mixture : ν_{\max} 2800–2950 (N–H, salts of secondary amine),

1560–1590 (bending, secondary amine salt), 1062–1070 cm⁻¹ (C–S–C), and characteristic absorptions of thiazole and benzenoid nuclei: δ (CDCl₃) 2.39 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.07–7.91 (9H, m, ArH) and no signal due to NH up to δ 9.

5-Bromoacyl-2-mercapto-4-methyl-1-phenylimidazole (2B-a) : A mixture of 5-acyl-2-mercapto-4-methyl-1-phenylimidazole (1B-a; 0.01 mol, 2.32 g) and phenyltrimethylammonium tribromide (0.01 mol, 3.76 g) was refluxed in acetic acid (25 ml) for 2 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled and poured on crushed ice. The solid formed was isolated and crystallized from aqueous alcohol : ν_{\max} 700–1000 (C–H bend aromatic and C–Br stretch), 1050–1240 (C–H), 1320–1520 (C–H bend and C=C stretch), 1550–1610 (C=C, C=N and C=O), ~2460 (S–H), 3070 (C–H aromatic) and ~3230 cm⁻¹ (overtone of C=O stretch); δ (CDCl₃) 2.55 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.7 (2H, s, COCH₂Br), 7.2–7.8 (5H, m, ArH) and mercaptan proton peak was not seen up to δ 9.5.

3-[1'-Phenyl-2'-mercapto-4'-methylimidazol-5'-yl]-1,4-benzothiazine hydrobromide (3B-a) : A mixture of 1-phenyl-2-mercapto-4-methyl-5-bromoacetylimidazole (2B-a; 0.01 mol, 3.02 g) and 2-aminobenzenethiol (0.01 mol, 1.20 ml) was refluxed in ethanol for 3 h. It was then cooled and poured on crushed ice. The solid formed was crystallized from ethanol : ν_{\max} 640–990 (C–H bend aromatic), 1080–1180 (C–N), 1350–1610 (C–H bend, C=N and C=C stretch), ~2465 (S–H), 3060–3190 (C–H aromatic) and ~3280 cm⁻¹ (N–H); δ (CDCl₃) 2.6 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.1–7.7 (9H, m, ArH), 8.3–8.4 (1H, s, NH) and mercaptan proton peak was not seen up to δ 9.5.

Acknowledgement

Two of the authors (V.S.I. and R.V.D.) are thankful to U.G.C., New Delhi, for the award of Teacher Fellowships. The authors also thank Dr. D. B. Ingle, Professor (Retd.), Department of Chemistry, Dr. B. A. M. University, Aurangabad, for his invaluable guidance.

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